

Survey Antibiotics in the Outpatient Treatment of Upper Respiratory Tract Infections

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ABSTRACT

Aim: (1) Survey on the current situation of antibiotic prescription (2) Assess the safety–reasonability of antibiotic prescription.

Subject and Method: A retrospective descriptive study on 300 outpatient prescriptions at Vo Truong Toan University Hospital from August 2021 to August 2022 with the diagnosis of upper respiratory tract infection. Several factors associated with unknown antibiotics were analyzed by the logistic regression model.

Result: Cephalosporin antibiotics account for the highest proportion (42.8%), followed by fluoroquinolones (32.8%). Recorded prescriptions with interactions were 113 prescriptions (37.7%). In the total number of prescriptions (n=113), antibiotic interactions occurred according to: the level of drug interactions to Medscape includes close monitoring (75.8%). Next is the mild level (19.4%) and the severe level is (4.8%). The level of drug interactions according to Drugs.com includes the low level (61.8%). Next is the medium level (37.5%) and the dangerous level (0.7%). The most frequent interaction pairs are ciprofloxacin plus methylprednisolone (64/300 prescriptions), levofloxacin plus methylprednisolone (8/300 prescriptions) and ciprofloxacin plus tramadol (9/300 prescriptions).

Conclusion: The most commonly used antibiotic is cephalosporin, which has many pairs of drug interactions that require close monitoring from treating physicians and clinical pharmacists.

KEYWORDS: Upper respiratory tract infections, antibiotics, interaction.

ARTICLE DETAILS

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1. INTRODUCTION

More patients visit clinics and emergency departments each year for upper respiratory tract infections than for any other infectious disease. There are more than 25 million office visits each year for acute upper respiratory infections. Otitis media, rhinosinusitis and pharyngitis are the three most common upper respiratory tract infections [1]. Clinically, the treatment of upper respiratory infections is rarely accurately diagnosed and based only on clinical symptoms, it is difficult to distinguish whether the disease is caused by bacterial, viral or other microbial infections, including: Most upper respiratory infections are caused by viruses. In addition, drug interactions also cause many disadvantages in treating this disease if clinicians and pharmacists do not clearly understand the common interaction pairs that occur when treating this disease. In order to improve the quality of treatment and use antibiotics safely and appropriately in patients I conduct research with the following specific goals:

(1) Survey on the current status of antibiotic use in outpatient treatment of upper respiratory infections

(2) Analyze drug interactions in prescriptions Antibiotic medicine at Hospital

2. RESEARCH SUBJECTS AND METHODS

Research subjects : Prescriptions for all outpatients .

Sampling criteria: Prescription with a diagnosis of ARI; prescription containing antibiotics.

Exclusion criteria: Patients with concurrent infections other than NKHHT; prescription for topical antibiotics (ear drops, nose drops); The prescription contains traditional medicine and antiviral medicine.

Research time and location: at Vo Truong Toan University Hospital, Viet Nam during the period from January 1 , 2023 to December 2023 .

Research Methods

Study design: descriptive retrospective.

Sample size: 300 prescriptions.

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Research content: From the prescriptions in the selected sample, record and evaluate relevant information:

Characteristics of patients in the study sample: Gender, age, ARI, comorbid chronic diseases.

Characteristics of treatment drugs in the study sample: Antibiotics, duration of antibiotic use, supporting drugs.

Assessing antibiotic interactions in research samples : Evaluation standards using 2 tools Medscape and Drugs.com.

Table 2. Degree of drug interaction of these drugs lookup tool *

Tools	Level	Evaluate
Medscape	Contraindicated	If the interacting pair has both lookup tools present at the same time , it is recorded as 2/2 lookup tools; If the interaction pair is present in the same search engine, record the highest level of interaction in that search engine; If the interaction pair is not present in any of the lookup tools , do not record that interaction pair .
	Serious	
	Closely monitored	
	Light	
Drugs.com	Danger	
	Medium	
	Short	

Data processing and analysis method: Data were entered and analyzed using SPSS 26.0 software. The relationship is statistically significant when $P < 0.05$.

Medical ethics: The study was conducted after passing the medical ethics council of Vo Truong Toan University.

3. RESEARCH RESULTS

3.1. Characteristics of patients in the study sample

Age and gender:

Table 1. Gender distribution by age group in the study sample

Variable	Male	Female
	n (%)	n (%)
< 18 years old	23 (51.1)	22 (48.9)
18 – 24 years old	13 (59.1)	9 (40.9)
25 – 44 years old	37 (23.7)	76 (67.3)
45 – 59 years old	36 (47.4)	40 (52.6)
≥ 60 years old	24 (54.5)	20 (45.5)
Total	133	44.3

Comment: The median age in the study sample is 40 years old (Q1: 27; Q2: 53). The common age of adults with the disease is from 25 to 44 years old (37.7%). In women, the proportion is (55.7%); In men, the proportion is (44.3%). This difference is statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

Pathology of NKHTHT:

Table 2. Distribution of ARI pathology in the study sample

Variable	n	%
Number of pathologies	1 pathology	297
	2 diseases*	3
Types of diseases	Common cold	6
	Sore throat	184
	Tonsillitis	first
	Otitis media	19
	Acute sinusitis	93

Note: * Pharyngitis and tonsillitis; pharyngitis and sinusitis.

Comment: Among NKHHT diseases, the proportion of patients with sore throat is (60.7%). Next are acute sinusitis (30.7%), otitis media (6.3%), common cold (2.0%), and tonsillitis (0.3%).

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3.2. Characteristics of treatment drugs in the study sample

Proportion of prescribed antibiotic groups:

Figure 1. Treatment groups assigned to patients in the study sample

Comment: Cephalosporin antibiotics account for the highest proportion (42.8%), followed by fluoroquinolone group (32.8%) .

Antibiotics are indicated in respiratory infections

The majority of prescriptions did not contain antibiotic combinations (96.7%). Prescriptions with indications for antibiotic combination were (3.3%). Of which, (3%) is a combination of 2 antibiotics and (0.3%) is a combination of 3 antibiotics. Antibiotics indicated in the treatment of infectious diseases are presented in Table 5.

Table 3. Antibiotics indicated in the treatment of bacteremia were surveyed

Antibiotic	Common cold	Sore throat	Tonsillitis	Otitis media	Acute sinusitis
	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Penicillin	2 (33.3)	41 (22.3)	0 (0)	3 (15.8)	13 (14.0)
Cephalosporins	2 (33.3)	78 (42.4)	0 (0)	3 (15.8)	47 (50.5)
Fluoroquinolone	2 (33.3)	55 (29.9)	0 (0)	7 (36.8)	32 (34.4)
Macrolides	0 (0)	5 (2.7)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Lincosamide	0 (0)	-	0 (0)	2 (10.5)	-
Penicillin + Fluoroquinolone	0 (0)	2 (1,1)	0 (0)	4 (21.1)	1 (1,1)
Penicillin + Cephalosporin	0 (0)	1 (0.5)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Cephalosporin + Fluoroquinolone	0 (0)	1 (0.5)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Cephalosporin + 5-nitroimidazole + Macrolide	0 (0)	1 (0.5)	1 (100.0)	0 (0)	0 (0)

Comment: In pharyngitis, cephalosporin monotherapy accounts for (42.2%). Next is the fluoroquinolone group (29.9%), penicillin (22.3%) and macrolide (2.7%). Regarding the combination of penicillin + fluoroquinolone, it is (1.1%), the combination of penicillin + cephalosporin; cephalosporin + fluoroquinolone; and cephalosporin + 5-nitroimidazole + macrolide account for equal proportions (0.5%). In otitis media, fluoroquinolone monotherapy accounts for (36.8%), followed by penicillin and cephalosporin accounting for an equal proportion (15.8%) and lincosamide (10.5%). Combination of penicillin + fluoroquinolone (21.1%). In acute sinusitis, cephalosporin monotherapy is (50.5%). Next is the fluoroquinolone group (34.4%), penicillin (14.0%). Regarding the combination of penicillin + fluoroquinolone with 1 indication (1.1%).

Antibiotics are indicated for special subjects :

Among the 300 prescriptions surveyed, there are 3 special groups: children, the elderly and pregnant women.

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Table 4. Antibiotics we're not used on STDs in the study sample

Variable	TE	NCT	PNCT
	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Penicillin	14 (30.4)	16 (33.3)	-
Cephalosporins	29 (63.0)	14 (29.2)	1 (100.0)
Fluoroquinolone	-	16 (33.3)	-
Macrolides	3 (6.5)	1 (2,1)	-
5 - nitroimidazole	-	1 (2,1)	-

Comment: Antibiotics used in TE include cephalosporin (63.0%), penicillin (30.4%), and macrolide (6.5%). In the elderly, the penicillin group and the fluoroquinolone group were prescribed at the same rate (33.3%). Next, the cephalosporin group (29.2%), the macrolide group and the 5-nitroimidazole group have an equal ratio (2.1%). In pregnant women, cephalosporin antibiotics are prescribed 1 time.

Duration of antibiotic treatment:

Figure 2. Time to prescribe antibiotics in the research sample

Comment: The average duration of antibiotic prescription is $6.94 \pm 1,814$ days (GTNN: 1 – GTLN: 14). The duration of antibiotic prescription is more than 7 days (5.7%) and less than 5 days (5.0%).

3.3. Evaluation of antibiotic interactions in research samples

Table 5 . Results of antibiotic interaction assessment

Variable	n	%
KS interaction	Have	113 37.7
	Are not	187 62.3
KS interaction	Medscape	124 100.0
	Serious	6 4.8
	Closely monitored	ninety four 75.8
	Light	24 19.4
	Drugs.com	136 100.0
Short	84 61.8	
Medium	51 37.5	
Danger	first 0.7	

Comment: Receiving prescriptions with interacting drugs was 113 prescriptions (37.7%). In the total number of prescriptions (n=113), antibiotic interactions occurred: the level of drug interactions according to Medscape includes close monitoring (75.8%). Next is the mild level (19.4%) and the severe level is (4.8%). The level of drug interactions according to Drugs.com includes low levels (61.8%). Next is the average level (37.5%) and the dangerous level is (0.7%).

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Table 5 . Common interacting pairs

Interactive pair	Quantity	Ratio %
Ciprofloxacin + methylprednisolone	sixty four	21.33
Levofloxacin + methylprednisolone	8	2.67
Ciprofloxacin + tramadol	9	3

Comment: Note that the most frequent interaction pairs are ciprofloxacin with methylprednisolone (64/300 prescriptions), levofloxacin with methylprednisolone (8/300 prescriptions) and ciprofloxacin with tramadol (9/300 prescriptions).

4. DISCUSSION

Research results show that beta-lactam antibiotics, fluoroquinolones, and macrolides are the most commonly prescribed antibiotic groups and are commonly found in most prescriptions. Among them, the cephalosporin group of antibiotics is the most commonly prescribed (42.8%) . My results are similar to a study by Higashi T and Fukuhara S , cephalosporin accounted for the highest proportion (49.0%) [3] . But when compared to the study of Hashmi H and colleagues, penicillin group (54.9%) is more popular than cephalosporin (17.0%). [2] . The beta -lactam group has a wide spectrum of effects including Gram-positive bacteria (such as Streptococcus ...), Gram-negative bacteria (Haemophilus influenzae , Moraxella ,...) and anaerobic bacteria (such as Bacteroides ,...) and is also a group of antibiotics used First-line recommendations in infectious diseases . Besides, this is also the group with the highest unreasonable rate. A moxycillin is combined with clavulanate in different ratios so they cannot be substituted. Among the survey applications, amoxicillin was combined with clavulanate using 2 tablets/time instead of 1 tablet/time. Combination between amoxicillin/ Clavulanate + cefixime is an inappropriate combination due to overlapping pharmacological groups (beta-lactam group). This combination is not very effective but also increases the cost of treatment, increases toxicity, and increases the likelihood of complications resistant to available antibiotics . Group Fluoroquinolone accounts for a fairly high proportion (32.8 %) . Fluoroquinolones , because of their unnecessarily broad-spectrum activity, potential for peripheral damage, and high cost, are hardly recommended as a priority choice [5] . In addition, the FDA and Drug Administration have also warned about the safety of fluoroquinolone, side effects related to tendons, muscles, bones, nerves, etc. This is only a reserve drug for patients who do not have other alternatives. The macrolide group (azithromycin and clarithromycin) is not recommended for empirical treatment due to the high rate of resistance to S. pneumoniae (about 30%) [4] . This group of antibiotics may be selected if the patient is allergic to beta-lactams.

5. CONCLUSION

From the above research results, we conclude that the most commonly used antibiotics are cephalosporins. There are many pairs of drug interactions that require close monitoring from treating physicians and clinical pharmacists.

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